

Design and Analysis of a Linear 4-Patch Antenna System for 5/6G Technology

Maria Sîrbu-Drăgan

Dept. Telecommunications
Faculty of Electronics,
Telecommunications and Information
Technology, The National University of
Science and Technology
POLITEHNICA Bucharest
Bucharest, Romania
maria.dragan@upb.ro

Teodora-Cristian Stoian

Dept. Telecommunications
Faculty of Electronics,
Telecommunications and Information
Technology, The National University of
Science and Technology
POLITEHNICA Bucharest
Bucharest, Romania
teodora.stoian@upb.ro

Simona Halunga

Dept. Telecommunications
Faculty of Electronics,
Telecommunications and Information
Technology, The National University of
Science and Technology
POLITEHNICA Bucharest & Academy
of Romanian Scientists (AOSR)
Bucharest, Romania
simona.halunga@upb.ro

Petru Mazăre

National Association of the Reserve
and Retired Military Personnel
Bucharest, Romania
petru_mazare@yahoo.com

Diana Brînară

Dept. Telecommunications
Faculty of Electronics,
Telecommunications and Information
Technology, The National University of
Science and Technology
POLITEHNICA Bucharest
Bucharest, Romania
diana.brinaru@upb.ro

Abstract— In 5/6G technology, antennas and antenna systems play a key role in ensuring high-speed, low-latency, and high-reliability wireless communication. Due to their compact size, high gain, and easy integration, patch antenna arrays are frequently used in the sub-6 GHz and mmWave (millimeter-wave) bands, supporting applications such as IoT, smart cities, and autonomous vehicles. Developing efficient and adaptable antenna systems is essential to meet the ever-increasing demands of 5/6G networks. This article aims to create a linear 4-patch antenna system that can be easily used and integrated into mobile communications, satellites, or drones applications that can be used in different IoT, environmental monitoring and precision agriculture. The system performance will be studied by analyzing various parameters such as reflection coefficient, gain VSWR (Voltage Standing Wave Ratio). This work seeks to obtain the best possible gain value of the linear system in the 5/6G high-frequency spectrum.

Keywords — 3D EM, 5/6G technology, antenna system, gain, linear system, patch antenna, reflection coefficient, VSWR

I. INTRODUCTION

Patch antennas are flat compact microstrip devices that uses a rectangular or square-shaped radiating element mounted on a dielectric plate. They antennas are commonly used in high frequency telecommunication systems due to their reduced costs and good performances in terms of directivity and efficiency, as well as their small size. Patch antennas are essential for achieving an efficient and scalable infrastructure in 5/6G networks, being used to meet the requirements of high capacity, low latency, and extended coverage.

Many researchers focused their attention on developing 5/6G antenna systems for different applications. In [1], the authors focus on improving the design of rectangular microstrip antennas (MPA) for 5/6G and future wireless communications. Given the increasing demand for high-

capacity communications, this work seeks to design an improved antenna that meets these requirements. The proposed antenna operates at a center frequency of 31.5 GHz, using an FR4 substrate, that has a dielectric constant of 4.4 and a thickness of 1.6 mm. It was designed and simulated using High Frequency Simulation Software (HFSS). The antenna achieves a return loss of -28.39 dB, a gain of 7.04 dB, a directivity of 8.25 dB, and a bandwidth of 4.9 GHz. In comparison with other MPAs presented in recent studies, the antenna presented in [1] exhibits substantial improvements with respect to the return loss and the achieved bandwidth, making it a strong candidate for 5G and future wireless communication systems. The authors of [2] focus on optimizing a wearable microstrip antenna for 5G that works at 28 GHz. After reviewing existing designs, the authors propose an improved antenna with adjusted parameters like size, geometry, and frequency tuning. This led to an important increase in the values achieved for the S -parameters, from -14 dB to -22.888 dB, while preserving the bandwidth. The antenna also achieved good radiation properties and efficiencies of 74.53% and 74.15%, proving its suitability for wearable applications. This work highlights future research opportunities in 5G-enabled applications like IoT and health monitoring, contributing to enhanced wearable antenna technology and 5G communication systems. In [3], the authors explore the evolution of wireless communications from the first to the fifth generation, highlighting the need for high-bandwidth antennas to handle large volumes of data. MPA antennas are particularly effective for portable wireless devices due to their small design, affordability, and ease of fabrication. The study examines how various factors, such as the type and height of the substrate, as well as the shape of the radiating patch, can influence the performance of MPAs. The research specifically investigates the impact of different shapes – square, rectangle, triangle, circle, E, H, and T – on antenna performance. Using FR4, a flame-retardant woven glass-

reinforced epoxy resin, as the substrate, the antennas were simulated at a frequency of 28 GHz using HFSS simulator. The results showed that the rectangular shape outperformed the others, achieving the highest gain, directivity, and notable bandwidth. The research presented in [4] analyzes the performance of rectangular microstrip antennas, aiming to evaluate the influence of the feed length and conductor materials (copper, gold and aluminum) on the antenna performance. The study uses finite integration techniques (FIT) to examine a design intended to operate at a frequency of 28 GHz, in the range of 20-36 GHz. The antenna was tested with different conductor materials, and the results show that aluminum offered the best performance, with a return loss (S_{11}) of -33.29 dB and a bandwidth of 976 MHz. Gold and copper achieved fine performance too, but not as good as aluminum. Regarding the directivity and gain parameters, all conductors obtained similar values, of around 6.99 dBi for directivity and approximately 6.6 dBi for gain. Thus, aluminum proved to be the most efficient conductor in this context. The authors of [5] focuses on the developing and implementation of a microstrip patch antenna operating at 28 GHz, which is intended for use in future 5G communication systems. The antenna has been developed using a Rogers RT/Duroid 5880 substrate with a dielectric constant of 2.2 and a thickness of 0.3451 mm. The simulation was performed using CST software. The results of the study show impressive performance characteristics for the antenna, including a reflection coefficient of -38.348 dB, a gain of 8.198 dB, a radiation efficiency of 77%, and a sidelobe level of -18.3 dB. These results demonstrate that the designed antenna has very good performance. The authors conclude that this antenna could be a strong candidate for implementation in 5G systems, offering superior results compared to existing antennas discussed in the recent scientific literature. In [6] is presented the development, simulation and physical implementation of a microstrip antenna arrays optimized for 5G applications with 28 GHz millimeter waves. The authors developed patch arrays, 1×2 and 4×1 , showing progressive performance improvements. The 4×1 array achieved the highest gain of 13.8 dB and a reflection coefficient of -41.4 dB, making it very suitable for 5G systems. Using CST simulations and a Rogers RT5880 substrate, the antennas were designed to be compact, efficient and easy to fabricate. The authors of [7] presents a dual microband patch antenna (MPA) designed for 5G communications at 2.4 GHz and 5.8 GHz. The antenna uses a graphene patch on a RT-duroid 5880 substrate and incorporates a complementary square triangle resonator (SSTR) metamaterial to improve gain and bandwidth. The results obtained in ANSYS HFSS show improved performance, with gains of 1.84 dB and 2.20 dB and return losses of -10.6 dB and -4.2 dB at the two target frequencies. Compared with existing designs, the proposed antenna offers better efficiency and is suitable for modern dual-band 5G communication systems. In [8] is presented a dual-band, dual-polarization, parasitic-element antenna designed for 5G Antenna-in-Package (AiP) applications at millimeter-wave frequencies (28 and 39 GHz). To reduce the power losses typically caused by long feed lines on PCBs, the antenna is integrated into a compact AiP structure. Parasitic elements

are used to enable dual-band operation by creating a second resonance, while the design also minimizes cross-polarization through strategic array orientation. Simulations and full-wave measurements confirm the efficient performance of the antenna, making it a promising solution for 5G user equipment. [9] is a review article that explores the development and applications of microstrip patch antennas, especially in the context of 5G and upcoming 6G technologies. These antennas are lightweight, low-profile, and suitable for a wide range of applications, including biomedical devices, autonomous vehicles, V2V communications, IoT, radar, and artificial intelligence-based systems. The paper discusses various antenna geometries, design parameters, analysis methods, and performance metrics such as gain, reflection coefficient, bandwidth, and VSWR. In [10], the authors present the design and analysis of a rectangular microstrip antenna for 5G applications at 3.5 GHz. Two designs were fabricated using different substrates: Rogers RT5880 (Design-I) and FR-4 (Design-II). Simulations were performed for: reflection coefficient, VSWR, gain, efficiency, and radiation patterns were evaluated using CST simulations. Design-I outperformed Design-II, achieving higher gain (5.64 dBi vs. 3.13 dBi) and significantly better efficiency (86.9% vs. 51.56%). Both designs demonstrated bandwidths of over 100 MHz, confirming their suitability for 5G use. The simulation results closely matched the measurements in practice.

The purpose of this work is to design a linear system of 4 patch antennas that operates at a frequency of approximately 28 GHz. We chose this frequency because it is part of the high frequency range for the 5G technology spectrum. The designed system will be analyzed at the working frequency, and simulations will be performed to evaluate the reflection coefficient, the Voltage Standing Wave Ratio (VSWR), the gain, the directivity as well as other important parameters.

In the following section, the calculation relationships used in the design of the antenna system are outlined. In section III, the results of the obtained simulations are displayed, and in section IV, the main conclusions and future development directions are presented.

II. DETERMINATION OF THE DIMENSIONS FOR PATCH ANTENNA

This section presents all the calculation relationships used in the sizing of the patch antenna. The dimensions were calculated for a working frequency of 28 GHz and for the Rogers RT/Duroid 5880 HH/HH material [11]. The dielectric has the following specifications relative permittivity constant ($\epsilon_r = 2.2$), loss angle tangent ($\tan\delta = 0.0009$), thickness ($h=0.508$ mm).

Metal has the following specifications: weight/mass ($1/2$ OZ), thickness/height ($18\mu m$).

Figure 1 shows the patch antenna with the notations used to calculate the patch antenna dimensions. Here we used W to denote the width of the patch antenna, L for length of the patch antenna, y_0 for depth of the cutout; y_1 is length of the feed line, w_m is width of the feed line and g represents the width of the cutout

Figure 1. Notations used for calculating patch antenna dimensions

We start by determining the width of the patch antenna, denoted by W , using (1) [12].

$$W = \frac{c}{2 \cdot f_r} \cdot \left(\frac{\epsilon_r + 1}{2} \right)^{\frac{1}{2}} \quad (1)$$

The calculation continues with the determination of the effective electrical permittivity constant which is obtained [12] using (2)

$$\epsilon_{eff} = \frac{\epsilon_r + 1}{2} + \frac{\epsilon_r - 1}{2} \left[1 + 12 \cdot \frac{h}{W} \right]^{-\frac{1}{2}} \quad (2)$$

In calculating the actual length of the patch antenna we also need the correction for the patch antenna length which is given [12] by (3).

$$\Delta L = 0.421 \cdot h \cdot \left(\frac{\epsilon_r + 0.3}{\epsilon_r - 0.258} \right) \cdot \frac{\left(\frac{W}{h} \right) + 0.264}{\left(\frac{W}{h} \right) + 0.8} \quad (3)$$

The effective length of the patch antenna is obtained [12] using (4).

$$L_{eff} = \frac{c}{2 \cdot f_r \cdot \sqrt{\epsilon_{eff}}} \quad (4)$$

The actual length of the patch antenna is given [12] by equation (5)

$$L = L_{eff} - 2 \cdot \Delta L \quad (5)$$

The length of the patch antenna penetration channel for the feed line, y_0 , is calculated next. The conductance of a single slot can also be obtained by using the cavity model, as shown in equation (6) [12]

$$G_1 = \frac{I_1}{120 \cdot \pi^2} \quad (6)$$

where

$$I_1 = \int_0^\pi \left[\frac{\sin\left(\frac{k_0 W}{2} \cos \theta\right)}{\cos \theta} \right]^2 \cdot \sin^3 \theta \cdot d\theta \quad (7)$$

With the asymptotic values of the integral (7) substituted into (6) we obtain

$$G_1 = \frac{1}{90} \cdot \left(\frac{W}{\lambda_0} \right)^2; W \ll \lambda_0 \quad (8)$$

$$G_1 = \frac{1}{120} \cdot \left(\frac{W}{\lambda_0} \right); W \gg \lambda_0 \quad (9)$$

The mutual conductance is defined, in terms of the far-zone fields, as

$$G_{12} = \frac{1}{120 \cdot \pi} \int_0^\pi \left[\frac{\sin\left(\frac{k_0 W}{2} \cos \theta\right)}{\cos \theta} \right]^2 J_0(k_0 \cdot L \cdot \sin \theta) \cdot \sin^3 \theta \cdot d\theta \quad (10)$$

The input resistance is obtained with (11):

$$R_{in}(y = y_0) = \frac{1}{2 \cdot (G_1 + G_{12})} \cdot \cos^2 \left(\frac{\pi}{L} \cdot y_0 \right) \quad (10)$$

Setting $y=0$ we obtain

$$R_{in}(y = 0) = \frac{1}{2 \cdot (G_1 + G_{12})} \quad (11)$$

and, from (12)

$$R_{in}(y = y_0) = R_{in}(y = 0) = 50 \Omega \quad (12)$$

one can determine the penetration depth of the feed line in the patch antenna.

$$y_0 = \frac{L}{\pi} \cdot \arccos \sqrt{\left(\frac{50}{R_{in}(y = 0)} \right)} \quad (13)$$

The space between the feed line and the patch antenna, denoted by g , is chosen between 1% and 50% of the w_m .

The width of the supply line is obtained from (14)

$$Z_{al} = \frac{120 \cdot \pi}{\sqrt{\epsilon_r} \cdot \left[\frac{W_m}{h} + 1.393 + 0.667 \cdot \ln \left(\frac{W_m}{h} + 1.44 \right) \right]} \quad (13)$$

where it is imposed that $Z_{al} = 50 \Omega$.

Using these relations, we obtained the dimensions for the patch antenna used in the design of the linear 4-patch antenna system presented in the next section.

III. DESIGN AND ANALYSIS OF THE 4-PATCH ANTENNA LINEAR SYSTEM

In this section, the designed 4-patch antenna system and the results obtained from the simulations are summarized. The simulations have been performed in AWR DE software, for the reflection coefficient (in dB), VSWR, gain, E and H planes and 3D EM analysis.

Figure 2 shows the 4 patch antenna system designed in the AWR DE [13] program using the dimensions obtained in Section II. Based on this system, we simulated first the reflection coefficient. The results are presented in figures 3.a. Analyzing these figures, we notice that the frequency at which the system we designed works is 27.78 GHz, very close to the frequency at which we intended the system to work, that is, 28 GHz. The reflection coefficient at this frequency has a value of -23.21 dB, which is a very good value, because a reflection coefficient of approximately -23 dB means that only approximately 0.05% of the signal is reflected, which indicates an extremely efficient antenna in using the signal and a good adaptation to the impedance of the signal source.

Figure 2. Design of the 4-patch antenna system

Considering the reference level as -10 dB, we can determine the width of the frequency band. With the help of the markers m2 and m3 we obtain that the band is in the interval [27; 29.45] GHz, having a bandwidth of 2.45 GHz.

Figure 3. Reflection coefficient, S_{11} [dB] of the 4-patch antenna system

Figure 4 represents the VSWR of the designed system. We observe that it has a value of 1.189 at the operating frequency, indicating an excellent impedance match between the antenna and the transmission line, since it has a value lower than 1.5 which is considered the reference value. VSWR can also be calculated based on the reflection coefficient, using relation (6):

$$VSWR = \frac{1 + |S_{11}|}{1 - |S_{11}|} \quad (6)$$

Figure 5 shows the gain of the designed system at the operating frequency. We observe that we have a gain value of 12.02 dB at the frequency of 27.78 GHz. For a patch antenna, typical gains can vary between 6 dB and 12 dB, depending on the design and dimensions. A gain of 12.02 dB suggests that the antenna has excellent performance and can provide a concentrated signal in a preferential direction, which is ideal for communication applications where signal directionality is important.

Figure 4. VSWR of the 4-patch antenna system

Figure 5. Gain of the 4-patch antenna system

Figure 6.a. E plan (polar) of the 4-patch antenna system

Figure 6.b. H plan (polar) of the 4-patch antenna system

Figures 6.a and 6.b represent, in polar coordinates, the E and H planes for the 4 patch antenna system. In these figures, blue represents the variation of radiated power in the azimuthal plane, and pink represents the variation of radiated power in elevation. From the diagram for plane E , a fairly wide opening in elevation is observed, and in the azimuthal plane, 2 small secondary lobes with a low level are noticed. For the characteristic in the H plane, it is recorded that in the azimuthal plane the characteristic has 3 lobes (one main in the 0° direction and 2 secondary in the -30° and 30° directions), and in elevation it has a characteristic with 4 lobes with a lower level.

Figures 7.a and 7.b represent, in a rectangular system, the E and H planes for the 4 patch antenna system. In these figures, with blue is represented the radiated power in the azimuthal plane, while with pink is represented the radiated power in elevation. In the case of a patch (or microstrip) antenna, the E -plane and the H -plane are the two essential planes that are studied to describe the distribution of electromagnetic fields. The E -plane contains the electric field vector and the primary direction of wave propagation, its radiation pattern indicating the variation of the electric field intensity. The H -plane contains the magnetic field vector and the primary direction of wave propagation, its radiation pattern revealing the variation of the magnetic field intensity. Analyzing Figure 8.a, it can be seen that the aperture at -3 dB is 168.7° between $[-82.6^\circ; 86.1^\circ]$. The azimuthal component in the E plane reaches a maximum level of 11.39 dB. Analyzing Figure 8.b, we observe that the main lobe is defined between $[-11.3^\circ; 11.6^\circ]$ in the direction of maximum radiation, having a maximum level of 10.77 dB.

In Figures 8.a and 8.b, the 3D EM analysis of the linear system is performed. In the E plane, a broad characteristic is measured with a main lobe formed by 4 unseparated lobes and with 3 secondary lobes symmetrical to the main lobe that have a reduced level, with a directivity of 11.4 dB. For patch antennas, the typical directivity varies between 6 dB and 12 dB, depending on the design and dimensions. A directivity of 11.4 dB suggests that the antenna is able to focus the signal in a very specific direction, which can be beneficial in applications that require good signal focusing, such as directional communications or radar.

Figure 7.a. E plan (rectangular) of the 4-patch antenna system

Figure 7.b. H plan (rectangular) of the 4-patch antenna system

Figure 8.a. 3D EM - side view of the 4-patch antenna system

The current distribution in a patch antenna diagram shows how the electric current is spread across the surface of the antenna conductor during operation. This is crucial for understanding the antenna behavior and optimizing its performance. Figure 9 illustrates the antenna orientation and the corresponding current distribution.

Figure 8.b. 3D EM - top view of the 4-patch antenna system

Next, in Table 1, the results obtained from the simulations for the patch system discussed in this section are summarized, as well as the results obtained for this system adapted to a 50Ω input. This adaptation is necessary to obtain a versatile system for a standardized power supply. After adaptation, an improvement in the performance of the antenna system is observed by decreasing the S_{11} parameter and VSWR and increasing the directivity and bandwidth.

Figure 9. 3D EM and currents distribution of the 4-patch antenna system

TABLE I. RESULTS ACHIEVED BEFORE AND AFTER ADAPTATION

	Parameters				
	S_{11} [dB]	VSWR	Gain [dB]	Bandwidth [GHz]	Directivity [dB]
Before adaptation	-23.21	1.189	12.02	2.45	11.4
After adaptation	-27.29	1.09	10.75	2.53	11.8

IV. CONCLUSIONS AND FUTURE WORK

The aim of the article was to design a linear system of 4 patch antennas that would operate at frequencies in the high frequency spectrum for 5/6G technology and that would have the best possible performance at these frequencies. Following the design and simulation, it was observed that the designed system operates optimally at the frequency of 27.78 GHz, achieving the proposed objective. Following the analyses carried out through simulation, the desired performances for the designed system were obtained. We simulated parameters such as: reflection coefficient, VSWR, gain, analyses in the E and H planes, directivity, bandwidth and 3D EM analysis. We obtained, at the working frequency, a reflection coefficient of -23.21 dB, which indicates an antenna capable of concentrating the signal in a specific direction, and a gain of 12.02 dB, which suggests an extremely low signal loss. These values suggest a very good performing patch antenna system with high gain and very low reflection, which is ideal for most communication applications. Comparing the results obtained by us with the ones obtained by other researches, we can see that the authors of [5] and [10] designed and simulated a patch antenna with the same substrate as us, RT/Duroid 5880, obtaining similar results. However, with respect to the antenna gain at the central frequency, we obtained even slightly better results, with 12.02 dB versus 8.199 dB in [5] and 12.02 in [10], giving thus confidence that our design has been successful. For future work, we want to develop the research and practically realize the linear system of 4 patch antennas and measure it using a vector analyzer in a semi-anechoic chamber in an accredited laboratory. We want to compare the results obtained through simulation with the results obtained through experimental measurements.

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